

THE ROLE OF MATERIAL HIERARCHY IN MECHANISMS OF DAMAGE INITIATION

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SUMMARY

The objective of this research effort is to explore new mechanisms of damage initiation in composite materials with hierarchical structures. The main result of the work is a notion that initial failure in a material is governed by interactions between hierarchical levels and is linked to formation of nano-structured networks within the reinforcement phase. By understanding mechanics of these interactions, one can control and improve damage resistance of composite materials.

Keywords: damage initiation, failure mechanisms, toughness, stiffness, multi-level hierarchy, networks, rigid lines, stress intensity factors.

MOTIVATION

Toughness and multifunctionality are not yet well realized in the existing fibre-reinforced polymer composites. For example, state-of-the-art epoxy-based carbon fiber reinforced composites possess excellent stiffness and strength, but their toughness is limited by early damage initiation. Initial failure as detected by acoustic measurements and direct observations (through radiography and microscopy) is manifested in the form of multiple microcracks that originate at high stress concentration sites of matrix/fibre interfaces, then coalesce and develop into matrix cracks [1,2]. A threshold for the first appearance of these matrix cracks puts tremendous design restrictions in applications involving fatigue loading and leads to overdesign of composite parts. A breakthrough improvement of this threshold is envisioned through employment of a drastically different mechanism of failure initiation.

Motivated to find a new mechanism of damage initiation we turned for answers to composites encountered in nature. Nature's success in creating damage resistant materials seems to lie in the intelligent use of hierarchy to trigger synergetic mechanisms of deformation. Despite large diversity in microstructures of naturally occurring composites, one can identify a number of fundamental similarities (even for such different materials as bone and spider silk). They are assembled from a soft matrix phase and a hard reinforcement phase. Elastic property mismatch between the phases is three or more orders of magnitude [3]. Reinforcements are reported to have platelet-like shapes with high length to thickness ratio [4]. Matrix is found to behave as a nearly incompressible material [5]. Nano- and microstructures of natural composites are built in a multi-level hierarchical fashion [3,6,7]. In the view of this, the objective of the

present work is to propose a model of a material microstructure that encompasses most reoccurring structural features of naturally occurring composites and to investigate existence of an original mechanism of failure initiation. The work bases itself on the guiding hypothesis that failure behaviour is linked to quality of interactions within the reinforcement phase. In order to follow this hypothesis we develop a method that is able to account for strong interactions between reinforcements. The method is sensitive to mutual positions of inhomogeneities. It can also work with inhomogeneities of different lengths. This option allows indirect consideration of two (or more) levels of material hierarchy simultaneously.

METHOD

In the light that reinforcements in naturally occurring composites have platelet-like shapes with high length to thickness ratio and that their elastic properties differ from properties of a matrix by several orders of magnitude, rigid-line inhomogeneities have been suggested as a suitable tool for their modeling [8,9]. While significant efforts have been undertaken to study a single rigid-line inclusion, studies that deal with multiple interacting rigid-line inhomogeneities are hardly existent. The lack of efforts in studies of multiple interacting rigid lines can be explained by serious mathematical difficulties that arise when one tries to model interactions rigorously. In the view of these difficulties, analytical methods have shown to be a powerful tool when fundamental trends and “proof of concept” are primary interest of research. For example, a number of interesting physical insights into properties of nacre, enamel and bone have been provided by a simple chain model developed in [10,11].

Interactions

In the present work we introduce a new method of interactions developed for rigid line inhomogeneities that employs the duality principle between solutions of rigid lines and cracks [12]. Let us consider an infinite linear elastic solid with an arbitrary array of N rigid lines subjected to remote loading σ_{ij}^{∞} . The problem can be replaced by an equivalent superposition of two problems: (A) a solid that contains no inhomogeneities and is subjected to far-field stresses σ_{ij}^{∞} ; and (B) a solid that contains inhomogeneities with certain prescribed deformations and with stresses vanishing at infinity. The prescribed deformation on the i -th inhomogeneity is vector $\mathbf{d}^{\infty i} = (\varepsilon^{\infty i}, \gamma^{\infty i})$.

Components of $\mathbf{d}^{\infty i}$ are related to the displacement field \mathbf{u}^{∞} generated in problem (A) as follows

$$\varepsilon^{\infty i} = \frac{\partial u_1^{\infty i}}{\partial \xi^i} \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma^{\infty i} = \frac{\partial u_2^{\infty i}}{\partial \xi^i}, \quad (1)$$

where $u_1^{\infty i}$ and $u_2^{\infty i}$ are components of the displacement field \mathbf{u}^{∞} and ξ^i is a current point on the site of the i th inhomogeneity. Such superposition is a common approach in crack problems with the exception that crack faces are free of tractions. The problem (B) is then represented as a superposition of N subproblems, each containing a single inhomogeneity with the unknown deformation vector $\mathbf{d}^i = (\varepsilon^i, \gamma^i)$. The latter is a sum

of $\mathbf{d}^{\infty i}$ and additional yet unknown vectors that are induced at the inhomogeneity site by other inhomogeneities in the remaining $N-1$ subproblems. This can be written as follows

$$\mathbf{d}^i(\xi^i) = \mathbf{d}^{\infty i} + \sum_{j \neq i} \Delta \mathbf{d}^{ji}(\xi^i), \quad i = 1 \dots N \quad (2)$$

where ξ^i is a current point on i th inhomogeneity and $\Delta \mathbf{d}^{ji}$ is a deformation vector generated along the site of i th inhomogeneity by j th inhomogeneity in the j th subproblem. The j th inhomogeneity in that subproblem undergoes (not yet known) deformation $\mathbf{d}^j(\xi^j)$. Term $\Delta \mathbf{d}^{ji}$ reflects interactions between j th and i th inhomogeneities in the array.

The basic idea of the method is to represent $\mathbf{d}^j(\xi^j)$ on j th inhomogeneity as a sum of its average $\langle \mathbf{d}^j \rangle$ and the non-uniformity term $\mathbf{d}^j(\xi^j) - \langle \mathbf{d}^j \rangle$. Similarly to the method of crack interactions developed in [13, 14], we assume that the non-uniformity term $\mathbf{d}^j(\xi^j) - \langle \mathbf{d}^j \rangle$ has no effect on the surrounding inhomogeneities. This means that the vector \mathbf{d}^i induced on i th inhomogeneity line by j th inhomogeneity is taken as generated by j th inhomogeneity with the prescribed *uniform average* vector $\langle \mathbf{d}^j \rangle$ only. Summing up, vector \mathbf{d}^i on the i th inclusion in (2) can be represented as follows:

$$\mathbf{d}^i(\xi^i) = \mathbf{d}^{\infty i} + \sum_{j \neq i} \langle \mathbf{d}^j \rangle \Omega^{ji}(\xi^i) \quad (3)$$

where

$$\Omega^{ji}(\xi^i) = \begin{bmatrix} \Omega_{\varepsilon\varepsilon}^{ji}(\xi^i) & \Omega_{\varepsilon\gamma}^{ji}(\xi^i) \\ \Omega_{\gamma\varepsilon}^{ji}(\xi^i) & \Omega_{\gamma\gamma}^{ji}(\xi^i) \end{bmatrix}$$

and $\Omega_{\gamma\varepsilon}^{ji}$ is $\varepsilon^i(\xi^i) = \partial u_1^i / \partial \xi^i$ along the i th inhomogeneity line generated by j th inhomogeneity with the prescribed uniform $\gamma^j = \partial u_2^j / \partial \xi^j = 1$ in the j th subproblem. Similar definition can be applied to $\Omega_{\varepsilon\varepsilon}^{ji}$, $\Omega_{\varepsilon\gamma}^{ji}$ and $\Omega_{\gamma\gamma}^{ji}$. The averages of these characteristics over the length of a rigid line can be called transmission Ω -factors that are similar to transmission Λ -factors in the method of crack interactions. They contain information about orientations of inhomogeneities as well as their mutual positions.

By taking averages of equations (3) over the length of rigid lines we obtain the system of linear equations to determine coefficients $\langle \varepsilon^j \rangle$, $\langle \gamma^j \rangle$. For each j -th inhomogeneity the system constitutes two algebraic equations with two unknowns $\langle \varepsilon^j \rangle$, $\langle \gamma^j \rangle$ leading to $2N$ equations in total for N inhomogeneities. After the average vector $\langle \mathbf{d}^i \rangle$ on all inhomogeneities is determined, the actual vector \mathbf{d}^i that is variable along the inhomogeneity line can then be constructed from (3).

Another characteristic that was absent in the case of cracks and is quite important in the case of rigid lines is rotation of rigid lines as a result of the matrix deformation. Rotation can be found when $\gamma^i(\xi^i)$ become known. More specifically, rotation of the i th inhomogeneity ω_{21}^i can be determined from the following equation (see [15]):

$$2 \int_{-a^i}^{a^i} \gamma^i(\xi^i) \sqrt{(a^i)^2 - (\xi^i)^2} d\xi^i + \pi (a^i)^2 \omega_{21}^i = 0, \quad (4)$$

where i is fixed and no summation is implied, $2a^i$ is a length of the i -th inclusion.

Stress intensity factors

In contrast to cracks, rigid lines generate several types of stress singularities. We focus here on stress intensity factors defined as follows:

$$L_I + iL_{II} = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \sqrt{2\pi r} (\sigma_{22}(a-r, 0) + i\sigma_{12}(a-r, 0)), \quad (5)$$

where L_I and L_{II} are referred in this work as mode I and mode II interface SIFs, respectively, at the tip $x_1 = a$. In the case of an arbitrary deformation acting on the inclusion boundary, we have:

$$L_I(\pm a) + iL_{II}(\pm a) = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{\pi a}} \frac{\mu(\kappa+1)}{\kappa} \int_{-a}^a \left\{ \hat{d}_2(\xi) + i\hat{d}_1(\xi) \right\} \sqrt{\frac{a \pm \xi}{a \mp \xi}} d\xi, \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{d}(x_1) = d(x_1) - r$, $r = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \omega_{21} \end{bmatrix}$ is a rigid-body rotation vector. Interface SIFs in (5) are responsible for failure initiation at the inclusion/matrix interface.

Compliance contribution

Compliance contribution of a rigid line inclusion can be obtained in terms of interface SIFs according to [16]:

$$H_{ijmn} = -\frac{\kappa}{2\mu(1+\kappa)} \int_{\Gamma} \left(\frac{\partial L_I}{\partial \sigma_{ij}^\infty} \frac{\partial L_I}{\partial \sigma_{mn}^\infty} + \frac{\partial L_{II}}{\partial \sigma_{ij}^\infty} \frac{\partial L_{II}}{\partial \sigma_{mn}^\infty} \right) d\alpha d\gamma. \quad (7)$$

While there are different ways to calculate H_{ijmn} , for example, directly from stress state field, relationship (7) is particularly important as it establishes a direct link between local and effective material characteristics. These characteristics are related to mechanical properties that are difficult to improve at the same time: failure resistance and stiffness.

RESULTS

Naturally occurring composites often exhibit reinforcements of different sizes. This notion is quite persistent in studies of spider dragline silk that is known for its superior combination of toughness, strength and stiffness. It has been reported in the literature

that silk possesses bimodal size distribution of crystalline regions or, in other words, exhibits coexistence of small and large reinforcement regions [17]. The notion of bimodal size reinforcement regions and a highly ordered microstructure may have some important consequences on mechanical properties. An objective of a computer experiment in the present section is to explore these consequences with a particular focus on mechanisms of failure initiation.

Let us imagine a composite material that is loaded in x_1 direction by σ_{11}^∞ and is built of a soft elastic matrix and rigid line inclusions with two distinct sizes $2a^{small}$ and $2a^{large}$ such that $a^{large} = 10 a^{small}$ (Fig. 1). For the moment we assume that nothing is known about density of inclusions and their location. If one poses a question: “Where will failure initiate in such a composite - at large or small inclusions?”, the anticipated answer would be “At large inclusions”. Indeed, energy release rate W is proportional to the length of the inclusion and if small inclusions are 10 times smaller then the energy stored at their tips (per unit length) is 10 times smaller than the one at large inclusions.

Fig. 1. Composite material with (a) large inclusions, (b) small inclusions and (c) bimodal size inclusions.

Material failure will be triggered by larger inclusions as concentrators of higher stress intensities at their tips. Having said so, we wonder whether the mechanism of failure initiation where larger defects or inhomogeneities play decisive role in determining material failure behaviour can be avoided. Thus a different formulation of the problem is considered with a newly posed question: “Is it at all possible to shift failure initiation from tips of large inclusions to tips of small inclusions” and “if yes, what restrictions on the microstructure should be imposed to realize such a shift?”. It is somewhat transparent that we hypothesize that if such a shift exists it would be controlled through microstructure.

In the computer exercise, large inclusions are arranged in the staggered fashion as shown in Fig. 2 (blue inclusions). The relative spacing between large inclusions is fixed throughout the experiment. Small inclusions are now being added to the material. Their location is not known and orientation is fixed along x_1 . Coordinates of each small inclusion are determined from a single condition that stress intensity factor L_{II}^{Small} at its tips is larger than the stress intensity factor at the tips of any large inclusion L_{II}^{Large} :

$$L_{II}^{Large} < L_{II}^{Small} \quad (8)$$

This inequality constitutes condition for the shift of damage initiation from large inclusions to small inclusions.

The outcome of the computer experiment indicates that, indeed, there is a way to meet requirement (8). It, however, cannot be achieved with arbitrary positioning of small inclusions in the matrix. The placement pattern when this condition is satisfied is illustrated in Fig. 2a. For this specific case SIFs at large and small inclusions are different by about two orders of magnitude, namely

$$L_{II}^{Small} \cong 10^2 \cdot L_{II}^{Large}, L_{II}^{Small} > 0 \text{ and } L_{II}^{Large} > 0$$

Small inclusions were found to form pathways or bands between large inclusions. These pathways were constructed using an iterative procedure where small inclusions were added one by one and their precise position was determined from condition (8). The latter requirement could already be achieved with a single inclusion in the center of the band. The procedure was repeated until the connecting bands were established. Symmetry of the problem was used to optimize the procedure. In the process of inclusion placement a few interesting observations have been made. For example, the shape of the bands is noticed to be critically important. Even incremental translation of any of the inclusions in the band to the right or to the left would lead to violation of requirement (8). SIFs at the tips of small inclusions showed little sensitivity to their mutual position with respect to large inclusions. Large inclusions, on the other hand, showed high sensitivity to the precise location of small inclusions.

Now we come to the most intriguing result of this work that was discovered purely by chance. If more bands of small inclusions are added to the material as shown in Fig. 2b, stress intensity factors at the tips of large inclusions become negative:

$$L_{II}^{Large} < 0, L_{II}^{Small} > 0, L_{II}^{Small} < |L_{II}^{Large}| \quad (9)$$

The negative sign of L_{II}^{Large} is due to the fact that the average longitudinal strain acting on the interface of large inclusions transitions from being positive in the case of the homogeneous matrix to being negative in the case of an inhomogeneous matrix with lamellar bands. It may be said that the presence of double bands changes local stress state from tensile to compressive. The induction of compressive stresses on inhomogeneities that initiate failure is important as failure mode may be quite different from the one known to occur under tensile stresses. For example, epoxy matrices are known to undergo brittle failure through microcracking under tensile loads and ductile failure through formation of shear bands under compressive loads [18]. As internal flaws, shear bands are less dangerous than microcracks and therefore preferred as a mechanism of energy dissipation. If behavior of a polymer matrix is similar to behavior of epoxies, then it is anticipated that defects formed under condition (9) will be shear bands and not microcracks. Even though this statement requires further research, the performed exercise does indicate that there is a change in failure initiation mechanism.

CONCLUSIONS

A composite material with bimodal size inhomogeneities may be viewed as a hierarchical material with two levels of organization. In this case interactions between small and large inhomogeneities may be interpreted as interactions between different

Fig. 2 Placement of small inclusions that satisfies (a) condition (8) and (b) condition (9).

levels of hierarchy. Then the results from the previous section lead to the conclusion that the material with two levels of hierarchy can exhibit different mechanisms of failure initiation depending on the structure of the lower level. Failure initiation can be shifted from stress concentration sites of the higher level to the lower level (for example, from micro to nano inhomogeneities) such that material behaviour becomes insensitive to the presence of inhomogeneities/defects on the higher level. The new failure mechanism, however, can only be observed in composites with highly controlled structural organization: reinforcement phase on the lower level needs to establish lamellar pathways between reinforcements of the higher level that results in formation of a network-like structure. Moreover, by creating such a network, tensile stresses near dangerous stress concentration sites on the higher level can locally be transformed into compressive stresses. The current work puts forward a hypothesis that damage on the micro-level in composite materials can be improved by structuring of the matrix on the nano-level. Precise morphology of nano-engineered matrix will be dictated by the structure on the micro-level and linked to the interaction effect between hierarchical levels.

Our modeling results are in resonance with recent studies of deformation mechanisms observed in Haversian bone [19]. The latter consists of osteons surrounded by concentric lamellae. Despite positive experimental evidence that such a structure improves material behavior against failure, the underlying mechanism behind it has been obscure. The authors elucidate that “the concentric lamella makes bone insensitive to the presence of Haversian canals”. Moreover, the traditional mechanism of failure initiation from stress-concentration sites of canals is not detected. This positively reflects on bone’s ability to undergo high inelastic strains at the macroscopic level.

Our results bring to mind another phenomenon that was reported in the nineties [20] and later studied in detail [21] – an impressive increase of impact energy (by several times) for semi-crystalline polymers filled either with rubber or rigid particles. A drastic change in the failure behavior was observed in blends where interparticle matrix ligament thickness was smaller than a certain critical value. The effect was attributed to

crystallization of semi-crystalline polymers near the interfaces of particles that lead to the formation of a layer of preferentially oriented crystallites. When such a material percolated through the structure the overall plastic resistance of the material was reduced and brittle behaviour was avoided. Inspired by studies of spider silk, segmented polyurethanes with soft segments containing multiple levels of order developed in [22] also showed unique energy-absorbing properties. The enhanced properties were explained by the presence of crystalline regions within the matrix.

Above examples have an important similarity with our results – failure of a material is linked to the presence of “lamellar networks” between inhomogeneities (pores, particles, rods, etc). The presence or absence of such networks determines a mechanism of failure. We hypothesize that by understanding how these networks are formed one can control and therefore improve damage resistance of composite materials. We also take from this work a more general conclusion that a true potential of hierarchy lies in the intelligent use of material organization to tune intra-hierarchical interactions – interactions between and within hierarchical levels – for the purpose of creating synergetic effects on material properties.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Support of the European Commission through the project “Automated Preform Fabrication by Dry Tow Placement” (AUTOW) is acknowledged.

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